

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN PERIPHERAL ARTERIAL DISEASE AND ERECTILE DYSFUNCTION IN A TERTIARY HEALTH CENTRE

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ABSTRACT:

Background

The study aimed to determine the association between peripheral arterial disease and erectile dysfunction among men aged 40 years and above attending the General Outpatient Clinic of Lagos University Teaching Hospital.

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Method

This was a hospital based descriptive cross sectional study that was conducted at the General Outpatient Department of Lagos university teaching hospital (LUTH), Lagos State. A total of 350 consenting men were recruited after obtaining informed consent. Participant underwent evaluation for socio-demographic data and clinical assessment for peripheral vascular disease (PVD) and erectile dysfunction (ED). PVD was diagnosed using ankle brachial index and ED was assessed using sexual health inventory for men (SHIM) questionnaire. The presence of ED and PVD was recorded for each participant and those with neither condition were also noted. Data were summarized in 2 by 2 contingency table and odds ratio and chi-square test were computed to determine association between peripheral vascular disease and erectile dysfunction.

Results

A total of 350 participants completed the study. The mean age of the participants was 50.83+/- 8.3 SD. Sixty-four {18.28%} participants had hypertension while 32 (12%) had diabetes. The prevalence of PAD and ED were 14.9% and 66.7% respectively. The severity of peripheral vascular disease revealed mild, moderate and severe as observed in (39 (7.5%), 9 (7.6%) 3 (5.9%) participants respectively. Regarding ED, showed that a total 100 (43.9%) participant had mild ED while a total of 97 (42.5%) and 25 (11.3%), and 6 (2.6%) had mild to moderate, moderate and severe ED. Association between PVD and ED showed no significant relationship. [$X^2=0.415$, $p=0.520$], odds ratio=0.82.

Conclusion

There was no significant relationship between peripheral vascular disease and erectile dysfunction.

Key words: PVD, ED SHIM and Ankle brachial index

INTRODUCTION:

Peripheral arterial disease (PAD) is a disease of the abdominal aorta, iliac and lower extremity arteries caused by atherosclerosis which lead to stenosis /occlusion of the vessels.¹ It affects mainly the lower extremity.² It is the third leading cause of atherosclerotic cardiovascular morbidity, following coronary artery disease and stroke.³ It is associated with reduced quality of life, myocardial infarction and cerebrovascular disease. Individuals with PAD have a higher rate of all-cause mortality compared with those without PAD.

In 2010, an estimated 202 million people worldwide were living with PAD, with 67.7% living in low and middle income countries. In the United States, approximately 8.5 million individuals were reported to be affected.⁴ A study conducted in Nigeria reported a prevalence of 24.8%.⁵ As a marker of adverse cardiovascular outcomes, PAD often remains asymptomatic or undiagnosed. However, symptoms like intermittent

claudication, ischemic rest pain, ischemic ulceration, and limb loss may be present. Age, cigarette smoking, obesity, diabetes, dyslipidemia and hypertension are risk factors for PAD and erectile dysfunction(ED).

The diagnosis of PAD can be made using ankle brachial index (ABI). The Ankle-brachial index (ABI) is an affordable, effective, non-invasive and easy to use screening tool for evaluating PAD. Other modalities for diagnosis include duplex ultrasonography, computed tomography, angiography and magnetic resonance angiography which offer more anatomic information in cases where revascularization is required.⁶

PAD is primarily due to atherosclerosis which underlies other associated conditions like stroke, coronary arterial disease and vascular type of erectile dysfunction (ED).⁷ Erectile dysfunction is found to precede peripheral arterial disease and other cardiovascular diseases. It is associated with increased risk of developing cardiovascular disease

in men. Erectile dysfunction (ED) is defined as the persistent inability to achieve and maintain an erection adequate for satisfactory sexual intercourse. It is the commonest sexual dysfunction in men globally.⁷

Massachusetts Male Aging Study (MMAS) estimated prevalence of ED to be 152 million men in 1995 with projected increase to 322 million in 2025. The 170 million rise has been linked to increased aging population and lifestyle changes with more of it occurring in developing countries.⁸

As men age, ED prevalence increases in them.⁹ A prevalence of about 1-10% is seen in men below 40 years and 50-100% in men 70 years and above. In the developed countries like U.S.A., 22.5% prevalence of ED was reported. Studies done in Nigeria showed prevalence between 43.8% and 84.7%.¹⁰

ED can be caused by either psychogenic factors, organic factors, or both in some cases. Psychogenic factors are reported to be more common in men younger than 35 years and in elderly men who start a relationship with a new partner while organic causes are major risk factors in men as they aged.¹¹ It has been reported that up to half of men aged fifty years and above have ED secondary to vascular disease. Simple and effective tool like international index for erectile dysfunction -5 (IIEF-5) can be used in screening for ED, as most men with ED rarely present to Physicians because of stigmatization or low self-esteem irrespective of the effect on them, their sexual partners and society at large.¹²

These effects include psychological distress, depression, marital discord, low productivity at work and increase risk of peripheral arterial disease. Peripheral arterial disease and vasculogenic type of ED have been found to have similar risk factors and common pathogenesis.

These risk factors include age, cigarette smoking, diabetes, dyslipidaemia, hypertension and obesity. Studies have shown that both disease conditions are due to atherosclerosis, which is a complex process that involves oxidation of lipoprotein, atheroma formation, inflammatory process and endothelial dysfunction.¹³

Endothelial dysfunction occurs due to loss of nitric oxide biosynthesis at the endothelial level, this subsequently causes reduced blood flow, less relaxation of smooth muscles in the vessels, cholesterol build up in the vessels and plaque formation. The process is seen in all the blood vessels in the body including the penis, heart, brain and lower extremity leading to erectile dysfunction, myocardial infarction, stroke and peripheral artery disease respectively.¹⁴

The effect of this endothelial dysfunction usually manifest first in the penis before other organs because of small size of penile arteries causing erectile dysfunction to precede cardiovascular disease like PAD. Thus, because of this relationship that has been found to exist between ED and PAD, ED is seen to herald future PAD. Due to occurrence of former before latter, some schools of thoughts have suggested that screening people with ED can be cost effective for secondary prevention of PAD. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of PAD and ED, as well as assess the association between the two conditions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This was a hospital based descriptive cross sectional study that was conducted at the General Outpatient Department of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH), Lagos State. Lagos is a metropolitan state located in South Western Nigeria with a population of about 21 million. The population is multi-ethnic with diverse groups and the Yorubas predominate. LUTH was established in 1962 and has since been actively involved in the

training of both undergraduate and postgraduate medical, dental and paramedical students. It has a 760-bed capacity and provides care across major specialties of medicine to a broad range of patients in Lagos and its environs.

The GOP Clinic of Family Medicine Department provides primary care for all categories of patients including enrollees of National Health Insurance Scheme, students and staffs of the institution as well as general outpatients. Appropriate referrals for specialized care are made when necessary. It is run by Consultant Family Physicians, residents in Family Medicine and Medical officers. It operates between the hours of 0800 - 1600hours from Mondays to Fridays. All patients are seen irrespective of the medical conditions, age, or gender. The average number of all patients seen in a month is 2,050 (650 men that are 40years and above). A total number of 350 consenting participants were recruited after ethical clearance from the institution review board. Participants aged 40 years and above and sexually active within the previous six months were recruited into the study. Those with ankle-brachial index of > 1.4 , neurologic disease, and history of urethroplasty or lower urinary tract symptoms were excluded from

the study. Participants underwent evaluation for socio-demographic characteristics and clinical assessment for peripheral vascular disease {PVD} and erectile dysfunction {ED}. PVD was diagnosed using the ankle-brachial index, while ED was assessed using Sexual Health Inventory for Men (SHIM) questionnaire.

The ABI was calculated by dividing the higher of the two ankle systolic pressures by the higher of the two brachial systolic pressures. An ABI value of ≤ 0.9 was considered diagnostic of PAD, while values between 0.91 and 1.4 were regarded as normal. Participants with an ABI > 1.4 were excluded, as previously stated. PAD severity was categorized as follows: mild arterial disease (0.8–0.9), moderate arterial disease (0.4–0.7), and severe arterial disease (< 0.4). The severity of erectile dysfunction was graded as mild [17-22], mild to moderate [12-16], moderate [8-11] and severe [1-7]. The presence of ED and PVD was recorded for each participant and those with either condition were also noted. Data were summarized in 2 by 2 contingency table and odds ratio and chi-square test were computed to determine association between peripheral vascular disease and erectile dysfunction.

RESULT:

Figure 1. Recruitment summary

A total of 342 men completed the study as shown in figure 1. From table 1, the mean age of the participants was 50.83 ± 8.3 SD. Sixty four {18.28%} participants had hypertension while 32 (12%) were diabetic. The prevalence of PAD and ED were 14.9% and 66.7% respectively. The severity of peripheral vascular disease revealed the proportion of mild, moderate and severe PVD as

(39, 7.5%), (9, 7.6%) and (3, 5.9%) respectively. Regarding ED severity, 100 (43.9%) participants had mild ED while 97 (42.5%) and 25 (11.3%), and 6 (2.6%) had mild to moderate, moderate and severe ED respectively. Association between PVD and ED showed no significant relationship. [$X^2 = 0.415$, $p = 0.520$, odds ratio = 0.82]. Table 2.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Frequency (n=342)	Percentage
Age group (Years)		
40-44	84	24.6
45-49	94	27.5
50-54	64	18.7
55-59	38	11.1
60-64	37	10.8
≥65	25	7.3
Mean ± SD	50.83 ± 8.3	

Table 2: Association between erectile dysfunction and PAD status among respondents

	PAD		Total	X^2	p-value
	Yes (n=51)	No (n=291)			
Erectile dysfunction				0.415	0.520
Yes	32(14.0)	196(86.0)	228(100.0)		
No	19(16.70)	95(83.3)	114(100.0)		

DISCUSSION:

This study was conducted among men 40 years and above. The mean age group was 50.83 ± 8.3 years. This is similar to the findings of Oyelade et al. who reported the mean age of 46.7 years in a population based study conducted among men in South-western Nigeria.¹⁵ Also, Yeboah et al. reported mean age of 54 years which was close to the finding of this study.¹⁶

However, this was in contrast to the findings of Adeko et al. who reported a mean age of 62.5 years among adult's respondents in a hospital based study

conducted in Sagamu, Nigeria Adeko et al.¹⁷ Conducted the study among respondents who were 50 years and above unlike this study that was done among men of 40 years and above, this might be responsible for the higher mean age reported by Adeko et al. This study showed that 14.9% of the participants had peripheral arterial disease with $ABI \leq 0.9$ suggesting a low prevalence of peripheral arterial disease.

This was slightly similar to a hospital based cross sectional study conducted by Adeko et al. In Sagamu who reported the prevalence of 24.8%.¹⁷ This slight variation might be as a result of larger

sample size used in their study and age group studied which was 50 years and above. In older age groups, there is also a tendency for an increase in cardio metabolic diseases, which in turn serve as risk factors for peripheral arterial disease. Similarly, in a study conducted by Odenigbo et al. in Southeast Nigeria among adult hypertensive respondents reported a PAD prevalence of 24.8%.¹⁸

This difference may be attributed to the characteristics of the study population, as hypertension is known to predispose to peripheral arterial disease. Also, studies by Umuerrri et al. in Benin and Yakubu et al. in Zaria reported a higher prevalence of 35.6% and 29% respectively.^{19, 20} The variation from this study maybe due to the fact that both studies were conducted among participants with diabetes mellitus. This higher prevalence is expected, as research have shown that diabetes mellitus is an established risk factor for peripheral arterial disease. A sharp contrast was observed in the findings of Ismail et al. in Kano who reported a very high prevalence of 87.2%.²¹ This finding was not surprising as the study was carried out amongst individuals with suspected peripheral arterial disease.

This may have introduced some bias in the selection process in their study. Also, a Doppler ultrasound machine was used in their study as against this study where hand held Doppler was employed. This gave them the opportunity to visualize the vessels directly and may have aided the diagnosis of peripheral arterial disease among the participants.

In Ghana, Yeboah et al. found a prevalence of 26.7% among adult participants with diabetes. On the contrary, Bediako- Brown et al. also from Ghana found a prevalence of 71% among participants undergoing lower limb amputation. Although the instrument used in assessing for PAD was the same as the one used in this study.

However, this disparity observed maybe ascribed to the different study populations. They already had critical limb ischemia, which is one of the late presentations of PAD and is being managed by amputation. This was in contrary to relatively normal subjects used in this study

The prevalence of ED using the IIEF-5 in the present study was 66.7%. The prevalence of erectile dysfunction from literature ranged from 19.8% to 84%, with variations attributable to differences in study population, study design, participants' age, and associated co morbidities.²²

Consistent with the findings of this study, Adebusoye et al. in Ibadan reported a prevalence of 55.1% among the patients attending primary care clinic while Oyelade et al. in Ogbomoso reported a prevalence of 58.9%.²³ The high prevalence reported in these studies were consistent with the prevalence found in the present study. This agreement could be owned to the reason that the questioner used was interviewed administered. The respondents may be more willing to disclose to their physicians when asked about erectile dysfunction rather than complaining about it themselves. In addition, the similarity of these studies and the current one can be explained by the use of similar assessment tool, the IIEF-5, in assessing erectile dysfunction among the participants.

There was no statistically significant association between peripheral arterial disease and erectile dysfunctions among the participants of this study ($p=0.520$). This is in contrast to the thinking that there is an association between vasculogenic erectile dysfunction and peripheral arterial disease as they shared similar risk factors and common underline pathology which is atherosclerosis. There was no statistically significant association between peripheral arterial disease (PAD) and erectile dysfunction (ED) among the participants in this

study ($p = 0.310$). This finding contrasts with the widely held view that vasculogenic ED and PAD are linked, given that they share similar risk factors and a common underlying pathology—atherosclerosis.

There remains considerable debate regarding the association between peripheral arterial disease (PAD) and erectile dysfunction (ED). While some researchers have reported a significant association between the two conditions,²⁴ others— including the present study—have found no significant association between ED and PAD. Supporting this finding, Ozima et al. in Sao Jose do Rio Preto in Brazil reported in their study that the clinical application of ABI in erectile dysfunction showed the absence of PAD. In essence, there is no association between erectile dysfunction and peripheral arterial disease.²⁵

CONCLUSION:

This study has confirmed that there was no significant relationship between peripheral vascular disease and erectile dysfunction among the investigated group.

Conflict of interest:

There is no conflict of interest in this paper

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